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The Impact of Modernization on the Economic Life of the Oraons

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Introduction

The Oraons are considered to have the second-largest population of tribes in Bihar and Jharkhand. They are believed to have settled in the Chotanagpur plateau centuries ago. Oraons speak the Kurukh language which is related to the Dravidian family of languages. The Kurukh sub-stratum is very prominent in the language of the Konkani or Konkani language. Oraon is the nickname of the Kurukhs assigned by their masters, possibly with reference to their migration and their susceptibility to roaming. Oraons are divided into so many totemic clans like Ekka, Tigga, Barla, Kujur, Bara, Lakra, Tirkey, Bakhla, Toppo, Kispotta, Minz and Kerketta. The Oraons have no proper sub-tribes in the central province. Kuda and Kisan who are assumed to be the subtribes of the Oraons, regard themselves as separate tribes and avoid intermarriage with the Oraons. The majority of Oraon tribes are religious-minded people. They worship God and Goddesses but a great number of these tribes have adopted Christianity. In the ancient days, this community used to follow the Sarna religion. A large number of Oraons abandoned their original beliefs of Sarna. In fact, in the 19th and early 20th centuries Oraons faced tremendous trouble due to exploitation from British traders. Christian missionaries found Oraons depressed and without food. They influenced many Oraons to accept Christianity. Oraons today practice various religions and speak more than one language; they earn through livelihood from a variety of occupations.¹

Origin and Migration

The need for enumeration of the Oraon people is driven by their search for identity. This recent and crucial phenomenon applies to Oraons and the other communities known as 'Tribals' or 'Adivasis' in the Indian subcontinent.² Cultural identity of the tribals with political overtime involving a demand for separate statehood of Jharkhand called for more serious attention.³ The concept of identity also implies to common elements among various communities as well as their uniqueness.

The Oraons can be identified with their distinct features, even though there are some problems in enumerating the Oraons. First of all, they are known by different names in different parts of the country. Though the people themselves prefer to be called Kurukhar after the name of their language Kurukh, in Jharkhand and Uttar Pradesh as also in Madhya Pradesh they are called Oraons or Dhangars (Labourer or servant), in the Sambalpur district of Odisha they known as Kissan (Cultivator), Kora (digger) or Dhangar- kora. ⁴

The Oraon tribe or Kurukh tribe also spelt Uraon. Oran or Oram are an Adivasi group inhabiting nearby states across central and eastern India, Myanmar, Bangladesh, Nepal, and Bhutan. Traditionally, Oraon depended on the forest and farms for their natural and economic livelihood, but in recent times a few of them have become agriculturalists.⁵

The Oraons of Odisha have forgotten the details of the traditional story of their origin. The only point in their history of migration from the Chotanagpur area is generally remembered by the old people.⁶

The Oraons who constitute a major tribe of Odisha, concentrate mainly in the two adjoining districts of Sambalpur and Sundargarh. The original name of the tribe in their own language is Kurukh while the outsiders call them Oraon and Dhangara (especially the Christian Missionary officials and the people of certain localities in Sambalpur and Dhenkanal districts). While seeking the meaning of the word Kurukh, S.C. Roy has concluded by saying, “It may appear probably that the Oraons of Chotanagpur came to call themselves the Kurukhs in the double sense of the tribesmen of the traditional hero king Kurukh and also in the sense of a tribe of agriculturists, Krisan or Kurukh”⁷

The name ‘Oraon’ which is not commonly used in their own language, was most probably given by their Hindu neighbours who saw the Kurukhs with what appeared to them their monstrously impure habits and extraordinary proficiencies. They were thus called Raonapur or the progeny of Ravana, and Oraon is the present form of it. Another mythical story which explains the origin of the name Oraon is also given by S.C. Roy. According to this the Bhaya-Bhahin, the first parents of Oraons, having been born of the blood from the chest of holy ascetic their descendants came to be known as Uragon Thakurs or Uraons. The word Dhangara is derived from the local Hindi word which means an unmarried boy who works for wages. Now this name is applied to all Oraons in certain localities.⁸

The Oraon is one of them whose habitat is spread over the undivided districts of Sambalpur, Sundargarh, Mayurbhanj and most of Keonjhar. The Oraons are said to have passed through a hunting stage before they developed agriculture. They also claim the honour of having introduced regular cultivation in the Chotnagpur plateau. The antiquity and the migration of the Oraon are, however, little

known. Roy (1915) puts the original home of the tribe in South India from where they entered the Chotanagpur plateau and then spread to other parts of the country.

Economic Development: The Tribal Scenario

The development stands for economic growth and progressive social mobility. It also implies harmonious upward mobility with social justice. Economic development and social development are complementary to each other. In the context of tribal communities, development has to strike a balance between economic and social domains and has to be culture-specific. But right from the inception of planned tribal development in 1951 till now the approach, by and large, has been influenced by the macro culture of the country. The planners, project executives and ground-level workers have all addressed tribal development programs with the spirit of macro culture.⁹

The tribal communities in India are extremely backward and poverty-stricken. It is because several communities have continued in the pastoral shifting cultivation stage of the economy till today. As the pressure of population grew agriculture advanced and the forest receded into the background. With longer land mass coming under settled cultivation, it was possible to grow a variety of crops in different fields. But despite all, the economic condition of the tribal people cannot be said to have improved much.¹⁰

Agriculture in the tribal region has remained backwards due to natural, technological as well as institutional factors, whereas the acidic soil certainly acts as a constraint on increasing productivity by Indigenous methods. Inadequate irrigation facilities, lack of adequate extension facilities concentration of land ownership, etc add to the problem. The main agricultural produce in the area is rice.¹¹

The tribal economy is intimately connected with forests and their economy. The forest regions are, generally, inhabited by tribal communities who are at one of the earlier stages of economic development compared to other communities in the country. As the population engaged in the collection of minor forest produce is believed to be essentially tribal and dependent mostly on agriculture for the major part of its income, the low level of agricultural income makes it furthermore dependent upon the forest produce.¹²

The Department of Welfare for Scheduled Tribes and Scheduled Castes was established on 24th October 1970 to provide more focused attention on the integrated socio-economic development of the most underprivileged sections of the Indian society namely the Scheduled Tribes (STs) and Scheduled Castes (SCs), in a coordinated and planned manner. Subsequently, it was bifurcated as the Directorate of Welfare for Scheduled Tribes and Directorate of Welfare for Scheduled Castes in 1982. The

Department of Tribal Welfare is the Nodal Department for the overall policy, planning and coordination programme for the development of Scheduled Tribes.¹³

According to the Forest Survey of India, 2011, the total forest cover in the country is 692,027 Sq. Km. which comprises 21.05 percentage of the total geographical area of the country. The total forest in the 188 tribal districts in 26 states and Union Territories in the country identified as falling under the Integrated Tribal Development Programme (ITDP) is about 411,881 Sq. Km., which constitutes 37.25 percent of the geographical area in these districts. Therefore, almost 60 percent of the forest cover of the country is found in tribal areas. The states with largest forest cover in terms of absolute area are also states with substantial tribal population, Madhya Pradesh (77,700 Sq. Km.), Arunachal Pradesh (67,410 Sq. Km.), Chhattisgarh (55,674 Sq. Km.), Maharashtra (30,646 Sq. Km.) and Odisha (48,903 Sq. Km.)¹⁴ at the 58 districts, wherein the forest cover is greater than 67 percent, 51 districts are tribal districts.¹⁵

The tribal population constitutes 24.85% of the total population of Odisha.¹⁶ This significant bulk of the tribal population in Odisha remained outside the periphery of modern civilisation during the British administration as a result of the policy of isolation. With the emergence of an independent index and adoption of the Indian constitution, planning for the upliftment of these backward people and integration of tribal population with the nation as a whole was felt indispensable.¹⁷

Economic Development with Special Reference to Oraon Tribe

Traditionally main means of livelihood of Oraon are agriculture and hunting. Due to pressure on land, frequent famine and oppression of money lenders and landlords they started migrating in batches to tea plantations in Assam. Loss of land, increase in population, need for cash and atrocity by money lenders and Zamindar drove out a large number of Oraon to tea gardens.¹⁸

The working and living conditions of Oraons are seen to be unsatisfactory. Lack of proper housing resulted in illness and immoral activities as Oraon with traditional occupation migrated to tea plantations and absorbed in organised industrial work. This shift from unorganised to organised sector could not be smoothly adjusted by Oraon. Migration has considerably reduced the occupational hierarchy of Oraon as they have involved themselves in the industrial way of life.¹⁹ Although the wages of plantation workers are not better than neighbouring peasants, Oraons get absorbed in new working environments to find economic stability and a permanent source of livelihood.

They did not have such economic stability in their native village under precarious exploitation by rich peasants, landlords and money lenders belonging to non-tribal communities. Other

occupational facilities related to health, education, recreation, housing etc., motivated Oraon to develop a positive attitude towards their new occupation.²⁰

The government has launched development programs exclusively for tribal areas and tribal people with twofold objectives i.e. economic upliftment of tribal beneficiaries through income generating scheme and area development through Infrastructure Development Schemes under various sectors of State Plan. Urban and industrial development, the Government's initiative by the establishment of ITDAs in Oraon concentrated areas has created a lot of positive impacts on the development of education, agriculture, communication, drinking water, housing, health, and sanitation. Initiatives have been taken at the GP and Block level to create awareness among them of different schemes so that they can reap the benefits and become prosperous.

Implementation of the PESA Act in tribal areas has also brought a lot of change in the quality and pattern of leadership among the tribe. Oraon's occupation tribal pattern and means of subsistence have been changed. The currency has replaced the traditional barter system. Change is observed in their living pattern, social customs, food habits and dress patterns. There is increasing use of modern electric gadgets, mill-made clothes, cosmetics etc. The importance of religious functions has declined and, in many cases, the rituals are observed symbolically.²¹

The scenario has changed during the last few years. Two multinational companies Ambuja and Sahara Group made their appearance and took the agricultural lands from the Oraon families either partially or completely. The companies used the lands for some urban projects like building housing complexes, shopping malls etc. In return for the lands, they promised to give compensation. Oraons who still have cultivable lands in surrounding areas could not cultivate due to the developing urban projects as the main canal system connection to the river has been disconnected. In the absence of irrigation facilities, they have to depend on rainwater for cultivation. Under this situation, the Oraons who are doing jobs in Government and non-government sectors are economically better in position. But those who did not get any compensation or any kind of job are facing economic problems. They are still Waiting for the compensation.²²

Economic Life of Oraon

The economic life of Adivasis exhibits different stages of development. There are the practitioners of subsistence economy, e.g. Food gathering, hunting, and fishing (Birhors, Hill Kharias). Some tribes like the Juangs, Hill Bhuiyans, Kondhs and Kharia Saoras continue hunting and food gathering along with shifting cultivation. Even the regular agriculturists like the Santals supplement their income by hunting and gathering. In a few tribes, the economic unit is the family, such tribes are

the Kharias, Mankidi, Mankirdia, and Birhar and they are usually found in the forests of Mayurbhanj, Keonjhar and Sundargarh. They are very poor and live in isolated small houses and groups and their economy is continued primarily to the forest.²³

Oraon a tribal community recognised by the Government of India, inhabits mainly in Madhya Pradesh, Odisha, Bihar, Jharkhand, and West Bengal. The community in the initial days' due to economic deprivation and socio-historical problems created from within and from outside, migrated to the different regions of the state during the British period.²⁴

Economic transformation occurred due to migration and change of occupation from peasant economy to wage labourer. Such a process of uprooting the peasants for plantation work is a worldwide phenomenon. The traditional occupation of Oraon was agriculture and hunting. The nature of the suffering of plantation workers is different from other industrial workers. Working and living conditions of Oraons are seen to be unsatisfactory. Lack of proper housing results in illness and immoral activities. Migration has considerably reduced occupational hierarchy of Oraon as they have involved themselves in industrial way of life. In that the Oraons get absorbed in new working environment find economic stability and permanent source of earning for livelihood.²⁵

A majority of tribal groups work in primary sector, and are heavily dependent on agricultural either as cultivators or as agricultural labours. At the same time, a number of Scheduled Tribes no longer follow their traditional occupations and work as labourers on plantations or in mines and factories (in many cases, since the nineteenth century). Displacement and forced migration has also led to an increasing number of Scheduled Tribes working as contract labourers in the construction industry and as domestic workers in major cities. Over 80% of Scheduled Tribes work in the primary sector against 53% of the general population, primarily as cultivators. However, the number of STs who were cultivators, declined from over 68% to 45% in 2001 whereas the number of tribal agricultural labourers increased from about 20% to 37%, demonstrating increasing landlessness among tribals. This trend has intensified, as can be seen in data from the 2011 census. It is further estimated that, in the last decade, about 3.5 million tribal people are leaving agriculture and agriculture-related activities to enter the internal labour market.²⁶

The census of India is a rich source of employment data. It not only estimates the population but also indicates the status of workers, defined as those who have participated in any economically productive activity at any time during the reference period. The census classifies workers as main and marginal workers. Main workers are those who participated in any economically productive activity for not less than six months during the year. Preceding the date of enumeration, marginal workers are those who participated in any economically productive activity for less than six months during the

reference period. In the 2011 census, the population of Odisha was reported 4.20 crore about 3.47 percent of the population of the country. As per the 2011 population census, the total number of workers was 175.42 lakh, of which 151.04 lakh (86.1 percent) were in rural Odisha and 24.38 lakhs (13.9 percent) in urban Odisha. The male workers were 119.03 lakhs, which constituted 67.9 percent of the total workers and female workers were 56.39 lakhs, 32.1 percent of total workers. The main workers numbered 107.08 lakh constituting 61 percent of the total workers, while the cultivators were reported as 41.04 lakhs (23.4 percent of total workers) and agricultural labourers 67.40 lakh (38.4 percent of the total workers). In rural areas, the percentage of main workers to total workers accounted for 57.1 percent and in urban areas it was 85.5 percent. Further, it was also reported that the total number of marginal workers was 68.34 lakh constituting 39.0 percent of the total workers, out of which 81.9 percent were engaged for 3-6 months and the balance 18.1 percent were engaged for less than three months during the reference period.

Census data for 2011 reveals that there was an increase of 22.9 per cent of total workers in the 2011 census over the 2001 census. The proportion of male workers to the male population and female workers to the female population in the state stood at 56.1 percent and 27.2 percent respectively.²⁷

At present the economic basis of life among the majority of Oraon of Odisha is settled cultivation as the primary occupation. Paddy is the principal crops grown and rice is their staple food. Agriculture is supplemented by one or more subsidiary occupations, such as wage-earning, hunting, fishing collection of forest products, services and several arts and crafts. But it should be remembered that the ecological character of their surrounding does not offer sufficient opportunity to undertake hunting, fishing, and gleaning as profitable economic pursuits. Some of them have earned proficiency in several rural arts and crafts such as tile-making, brick-making, bidi-making, carpentry, masonry, etc. which bring them additional income in their leisure time. Some of them have taken up business, services of various types of wage-earning as their main occupation. They could have depended on agriculture but the pressure of population growth and their consciousness about the gap between their material wants and income have compelled them to compete with other people for new avenues of employment.²⁸

Conclusion

The Oraons who once upon a time were more conservative, are now in a transitional stage due to the impact of modernizations. The impact of mining and industrialization in their habitat and Christianity which many of them have embraced has changed their traditional way of life to a great extent. Government has launched development programmes exclusively for tribal areas and tribal

people with twofold objectives i.e. economic upliftment of tribal beneficiaries through Income income-generating schemes and area development through Infrastructure Development schemes under various sectors of the state plan. Urban and industrial development, the Government's initiatives by the establishment of ITDAs in Oraon concentrated areas have created a lot of positive impacts on the development of education, agriculture, communication, drinking water, housing, health, and sanitation. At present in Odisha, the Oraons have become one of the most progressive tribes. In the field of agriculture, they use chemical fertilizers, pesticides, improved seeds and modern techniques and hardly suffer from indebtedness. They have availed themselves of opportunities to improve their economic conditions through various special programmes like ITDA, ERRP IRDP etc. They are hard-working, and some family members temporarily migrate elsewhere for wage-earning during the period when there is no work at home. A majority earn enough to sustain themselves to purchase several varieties of modern and household articles. Their area has become accessible and many villages have approach roads and electricity.

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